

Abstract

The Impact of Acupuncture on Hamstring Flexibility: A Randomised, Blinded, and Controlled Pilot Study.

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Abstract

Background: Reduced flexibility is frequently cited as a significant risk factor for hamstring injuries. Acupuncture, a key therapeutic modality of Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM), is increasingly utilised in sports medicine to enhance muscle strength, improve microcirculation, and alleviate soreness. The primary objective of this pilot study was to examine the immediate effects of acupuncture on hamstring extensibility and the associated levels of pain or discomfort reported during stretching.

Methods: To account for individual variability and the constraints of a small sample size, a triple-arm crossover design was employed. Each participant underwent three distinct interventions: verum (active acupuncture at specific points), sham (needling at non-acupoint sites), and placebo (non-penetrating stimulation using a guide tube and wire). Flexibility was quantified using the Sit and Reach (SR) test, while subjective pain and discomfort were monitored via a Visual Analogue Scale (VAS). Assessments were conducted immediately before and after each intervention.

Results: A significant increase in flexibility was observed following verum acupuncture ($p = 0.03$), whereas no significant improvements were recorded in the sham or placebo groups ($p = 0.86$ and $p = 0.18$, respectively). Regarding the perception of pain or discomfort during stretching, no significant differences were found across any of the three conditions (verum, $p = 0.55$; sham, $p = 0.50$; placebo, $p = 0.58$).

Conclusions: The findings of this pilot study suggest that acupuncture may provide an immediate enhancement of hamstring flexibility, though it does not appear to significantly alter the sensation of discomfort during a stretch. These results support the potential of acupuncture as a preparatory or rehabilitative tool in musculoskeletal care, though further large-scale trials are warranted.

Keywords: Heidelberg Model of TCM; Acupuncture; Muscle Flexibility; Placebo; Traditional Chinese Medicine; Sports Medicine.

Citation: Matos L.C., Carvalho R.M., Machado J. Santos M.J.. The Impact of Acupuncture on Hamstring Flexibility: A Randomised, Blinded, and Controlled Pilot Study. *Journal of Complementary Therapies in Health*. 2026;4(2)

10.5281/zenodo.19889984

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Acknowledgements: This work was presented at the 1st Scientific Seminars of Complementary Therapies in Health, on 24 October 2025.